

FOREST4EU partner: GIS

OG: eGozd

OG's country: Slovenia

Type of Innovation: Service

Creating Your Own Estate Plan Via The Online Portal (MojGozdar)

Introduction

The project eGOZD has presented a web-based solution for developing a forest management plan. The solution enables the collection and interpretation of data on forest tenure, forest infrastructure and other data published on different publicly available platforms in one place using interoperability. Introducing the plans on farms owning forests promotes increased planned work with private forests and provides professional support for sustainable, nature and multifunctional forest management. It is coordinated with forest management plans, which ensure the sustainable conservation of forests and all their functions. A well-prepared management plan will ensure that the potential of the timber is properly exploited, contributing to the modernization and sustainable development of the rural areas. The project "eGozd" has developed new and simplified options for planning, monitoring and carrying out work and for more efficient private forest management (FM). The forest estate plan provides the forest owner with an overview of forest data and the possibilities for future forest management. The FM plan is linked to current prices for forest timber and tools for calculating the costs of timber extraction. Forest owners can monitor the performance of their forest estate and decide on the measures to be taken in the plan. The plan considers nature conservation guidelines and promotes habitat types, conservation or even improvement. A well-prepared management plan will ensure that the potential of the timber is properly exploited, contributing to the sustainable development of the rural areas. Using technical information systems, business processes can be digitised. By visualising and economically evaluating individual production processes, private owners gain better control over the costs of producing forest wood sorts. Forest owners can thus optimise their own different production processes on the same site, or the same production process on different sites, or even replace their own implementation by hiring a contractor due to their own costs being too high; this serves to decide on the most optimal implementation of the works.

Lessons learned

The estate plan will help agricultural holdings become aware of any constraints on forest management at the expense of management and the possible sources of funding or reimbursement of costs incurred due to the restrictions management options. The estate plan will specify/advise on and concretise the measures to be taken. The estate plans allow the owners to have an overview of the state of the estate with the existing forestry potential. It is an information system that is continuously adapted to forest management plans. It contributes to the conservation of biodiversity. One of the key advantages of interactive estate plans is the possibility to organise work, choose technologies and operators, and estimate production costs from forest to timber storage. This allows the forest owner to optimise the activities selected to implement the measures. Not only does the introduction of management plans ensure the transfer of new knowledge, but it also updates and optimises existing on-farm activities.

Figure 1: Overview of digital platform.

Figure 2: Overview of estate plan.

Posestni načrt

I. Opis gozjne posesti

I.1. Splošni opis posesti

Posestvo

Ime posesti	Črna Podgorja, privatna parcela
Površina posesti	17308 m ²

Parcela na posestvu

Parcelna številka	Katastrska občina	Površina na posesti [m ²]	Delež glede na celotno posest [%]
0625/222	2370	16657	97.3

Revidni podatki

Ime revizija	Revidni podatki	Številčnice	Kontaktne telefon	Površina na posesti [m ²]	Delež glede na celotno posest [%]
DTL.BCA	Mavrik Duvanjan	Gregorčičeva 44	05 306 14 88	16657	97.3

Gozdgozdpodarske enote

Gozdgozdpodarska enota	Gozdgozdpodarska enota	Ime Gozdpodarske enote	Površina na posesti [m ²]	Delež glede na celotno posest [%]
01	14	DTL.BCA	16657	97.3

For further information contact

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The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://www.mojgozdar.si/>

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